

A distributed multi-AUV control framework for cooperative missions

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Abstract—Intelligent multi-AUV systems are becoming well-established due to the advantages they offer in various underwater monitoring applications. One current challenge is designing and implementing distributed control frameworks to enhance cooperation between agents while accounting for the limitations imposed by the underwater environment. The only viable option for communication between agents underwater is acoustic communication, which is known to be unreliable due to low bandwidth, high latency, and frequent packet loss. In this scenario, we propose a sequential multi-agent decision framework to tackle monitoring missions that require explicit cooperation between agents. The cooperative mission is formulated as an optimization problem using a Partially Observable Markov Decision Process, in which each agent must meet specific operational objectives to improve the overall mission outcome. This work presents the software architecture developed to handle the guidance and control of the multi-AUV system and validates the proposed approach in a simulation environment that reproduces a cooperative monitoring mission while considering the major limitations imposed by the acoustic communication channel.

Index Terms—underwater mobile sensors network, passive acoustic monitoring, distributed motion planning, cooperative target tracking

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, there has been an increasing need to monitor marine environments for a range of applications, including biodiversity research and conservation [1], military surveillance, and civilian activity monitoring [2]. The use of Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) in such scenarios represents a significant advancement, as they provide a new level of autonomy to monitoring systems and drastically enhance their performance. The core idea is to leverage autonomous agents to improve the quality of information gathered by the sensors equipped on these vehicles. Research efforts across various disciplines, such as optimal sampling in oceanographic applications and sensor management [3], have explored strategies for sensor deployment and control to optimize relevant metrics during the mission. Generally, the problem can be framed as a stochastic control problem, wherein the degrees of freedom of the sensors are manipulated to achieve operational objectives, typically quantified by suitable cost functions. The pursuit of an optimal or suboptimal policy aims to attain a desired configuration of the sensors based on available information from prior measurements and environmental models while adhering to problem-specific constraints.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. The lookahead optimization scheme

Given the disturbances and uncertainties inherent to the underwater environment, a suitable approach for describing cooperative underwater missions is the Partially Observable Markov Decision Process (POMDP) [4]. While such methods can solve multi-agent optimization problems optimally, their computational demands are often prohibitive for robotic agents with limited resources. As a result, approximate solutions, such as rollout algorithms or model predictive control schemes [5], provide a balance between satisfactory results and computational efficiency, despite being suboptimal. Receding Horizon Control (RHC), which computes optimal sequences over a moving horizon, is a viable approach within such *limited look-ahead control schemes*. Consequently, we adopt an RHC algorithm to optimize the motion of the agents by adjusting their heading during the mission.

B. Sequential multi-agent decision making

The first attempts to address optimization problems within underwater sensor networks employed a *centralized approach*. For example, a POMDP applied to multi-AUV systems is presented in [6]. However, the major limitation of centralized optimization is the potential single point of failure, which compromises the entire monitoring system. This drawback reduces the system's endurance (a fundamental aspect in marine applications) and limits its applicability. In contrast, solving the problem fully distributedly is more resilient, scalable, and efficient, as network resources and workload are shared across agents [7]. In particular, it is possible to consider an agent's possible failure without compromising the multi-agent system. However, distributed optimization depends on the *joint action domain* of the multi-agent system, and solving such problems without overly complex state space solutions is non-trivial. The complexity increases exponentially with the number of agents when using a basic *greedy* approach. We implemented a sequential multi-agent (SMA) decision-making framework to achieve fully distributed planning. In this approach, each agent iteratively computes a rollout control policy and shares the resulting action sequence with its neighbors. Coupling RHC with SMA decision-making is particularly effective in scenarios where communication loss occurs, as each agent generates a sequence of control actions over a planning horizon H instead of just a single action. This allows agents to

PLANNING	RMSE (m)	σ (m)
Offline	110.7	60.4
Online	15.2	4.1

TABLE I: **Aggregated results.** The RMSE stands for Root-Mean-Square-Error and σ is the associated variance. The values in Table 2 are the average of 100 pseudo-Monte Carlo runs, the row "Online" contains the average of all experiments performed with the proposed adaptive planning method

approximate their neighbors' future states even in case of communication failure.

III. VALIDATION

As a case study to validate the proposed approach, we consider a Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM) mission. In this scenario, the agents measure the Direction of Arrival (DoA) of the acoustic signal emitted by an acoustic source, to estimate its dynamics. This problem type is often called Bearing-Only Tracking (BOT). It is well known that the observability of the target cannot be guaranteed for a single agent. Therefore, the key idea is to enable the agents to exchange measurements to triangulate the target's position. Previous studies [8] have demonstrated that the geometric arrangement of sensors relative to the target significantly influences the outcome of the estimation problem. Thus, the agents must move in a coordinated manner while tracking the target. This objective, along with operational goals and practical constraints, leads to a distributed optimization problem, which is addressed using the proposed distributed control framework, as illustrated in Figure 1c. As an initial validation, we used pseudo-Monte Carlo simulations over 100 runs to compare our system's performance against baseline approaches, where sensors are either fixed or move along predefined paths. The results are summarized in Table I. To test the system's robustness, we simulated challenging passive monitoring scenarios in an environment that explicitly accounts for the major limitations of the acoustic communication channel and the uncertainties introduced by the underwater environment. [9]. Figures 1a, 1b show the outcome of the simulator for a realistic passive monitoring scenario. To test the system's robustness, we simulated the failure of one of the AUVs. An Animation video of the simulation is provided at the following link <https://youtu.be/8JuXH7GXm3Q>.

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Fig. 1: **Simulation Results** Figure (a) depicts a simulation scenario in which three AUVs track a moving acoustic source. The symbol ξ represents the state of the target, while s_i denotes the AUVs. Figure (b) illustrates the trend of the cumulative loss function. The results are satisfactory since the loss function converges towards the optimal value, even after the failure of s_2 at $t = 300s$. **Software architecture** Figure (c) shows the software architecture designed for the implementation of the proposed distributed control framework.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. A. Mooney, L. Di Iorio, M. Lammers, T.-H. Lin, S. L. Nedelec, M. Parsons, C. Radford, E. Urban, and J. Stanley, "Listening forward: approaching marine biodiversity assessments using acoustic methods," *Royal Society open science*, vol. 7, no. 8, p. 201287, 2020.
- [2] M. F. Baumgartner, K. M. Stafford, and G. Latha, "Near real-time underwater passive acoustic monitoring of natural and anthropogenic sounds," *Observing the oceans in real time*, pp. 203–226, 2018.
- [3] A. O. Hero and D. Cochran, "Sensor management: Past, present, and future," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 11, no. 12, pp. 3064–3075, 2011.
- [4] M. Lauri, D. Hsu, and J. Pajarinen, "Partially observable markov decision processes in robotics: A survey," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 21–40, 2022.
- [5] D. Bertsekas, *Dynamic programming and optimal control: Volume I*. Athena scientific, 2012, vol. 4.
- [6] D. Song, W. Gan, P. Yao, W. Zang, Z. Zhang, and X. Qu, "Guidance and control of autonomous surface underwater vehicles for target tracking in ocean environment by deep reinforcement learning," *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 250, p. 110947, 2022.
- [7] C. D. Charalambous and N. U. Ahmed, "Centralized versus decentralized optimization of distributed stochastic differential decision systems with different information structures-part i: A general theory," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 62, no. 3, pp. 1194–1209, 2017.
- [8] A. Tiranti, F. Wanderlingh, E. Simetti, G. Indiveri, and M. Baglietto, "Motion optimization strategy for bearing-only tracking performed with a team of autonomous underwater vehicles navigating in formation," in *OCEANS 2023 - Limerick*, 2023, pp. 1–7.
- [9] M. Stojanovic and J. Preisig, "Underwater acoustic communication channels: Propagation models and statistical characterization," *IEEE communications magazine*, vol. 47, no. 1, pp. 84–89, 2009.